

Automatic Temperature Controlled Air Cooler: Design, Assembly and Testing

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ABSTRACT

Temperature control is defined as to maintain the temperature at desired set point. It is widely used process. In modern era temperature control is an important factor as it has many applications. Automatic temperature control is the best way to control the temperature automatically in any electrical appliance. This method has improved significantly in temperature control as it functions with least or minimal manual intervention. The result shows the temperature is controlled in an effective and precise manner. In addition, it was observed that Automatic Temperature Controlled Air Cooler was cost efficient as compared to the conventional air cooler.

KEYWORDS: Air Cooler, LM 35, Arduino

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1. INTRODUCTION

A temperature control system has a programmable thermostat that keeps the environment at a desired temperature. The advantage of having an automatic temperature control system over a common thermostat is that it saves energy and cost by automatically maintaining different temperatures at various instant. It has a closed loop feedback system having a control loop, including thermal sensors, control program and actuators/effectors, and is arranged in such a manner so as to regulate a variable temperature at a set point or reference value defined by end user.

A host of analysis of temperature control have appeared in literature [1-4]. These analysis employs the use of closed loop temperature control system which works according to the temperature of the environment. It was shown experimentally by Ahmad Faris Bin Zulkifli [1] that using temperature sensor one can control the room temperature of a region without any human intervention. Temperature control and sensor systems follows a conventional pattern. The sensor device senses the temperature and passes its analog signal to the Arduino unit for the micro-controller to

test and compare the temperature with the set-point. When this test fails, an effect tor system acts to correct the temperature and checks it back within the user defined range.

A difference in the design of our system over any other system is that the Arduino used does not have that much current to control DC Pump and DC Motor so a separate relay unit incorporated with a different power supply is used for this purpose.

In northern India, during summer season temperature is around 40°C. The maximum it reaches is 50°C. A common man in India cannot afford air conditioner and using conventional cooler incurs more cost. The Automatic Temperature Controlled Air Cooler solves this problem. The analysis and comparison for the above has been a part of our research.

This paper is organized as follows. First the governing equation. Second, circuit design procedure. Third, assembly and then result comparison with a conventional air cooler.

Observations of Automatic Temperature Controlled Air Cooler:

According to our observations in 80 minutes period, Motor and Pump, both were OFF for 65 minutes
Motor was ON for 15 minutes
Pump was not switched ON as temperature didn't exceeded the set point. Hence,
Total Power Consumed = $(65 \times 4.32) + (15 \times 18.72)$
=561.6 J/min

Total Power Consumed per hour = 561.6×60
=33696 J

4. Conclusion

In this research work, it was observed that the Automatic Temperature Controlled Air Cooler is cost efficient as compared to the conventional air cooler. The automatic cooler operates only whenever required while the conventional air cooler operates continuously even when there is no need. This automatic cooler minimizes the human intervention to the optimum level in comparison with the normal air cooler.

5. References

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